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Japan's Nation Branding Strategy Through "Cool Japan" Campaign and Its Acceptance Among Pakistani Youth

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ABSTRACT

This study explores Japan's cultural diplomacy with a focus on its nation branding strategy through the "Cool Japan" campaign and its reception among Pakistani youth. Drawing on theoretical frameworks of public diplomacy, cultural diplomacy, and nation branding, the research examines how Japan employs anime, manga, video games, and cuisine to construct a favorable global image. Using a mixed-method approach, including qualitative analysis and a quantitative survey of 190 Pakistani youth, the findings reveal a high degree of awareness and positive perceptions of Japanese culture. The majority of participants reported frequent engagement with Japanese cultural products, which significantly influenced their interest in Japan, lifestyle choices, and desire for cultural exchange. Results confirm that Japan's cultural diplomacy is highly effective in shaping positive attitudes abroad. Furthermore, the study highlights valuable lessons for Pakistan to strengthen its own cultural promotion strategies.

Keywords: Nation Branding, Cultural Diplomacy, Public Diplomacy, Cool Japan Campaign, Japanese Culture, Pakistani Youth

Japan's Public and Cultural Diplomacy

Signitzer and Coombs (1992, p. 138) define public diplomacy as a strategy through which states' governments, the private sector, and groups can influence foreign public opinion, which in turn influences foreign governments in their political decisions. Public diplomacy is expanding its sphere from traditional diplomacy, which concerns government officials, towards new actors, including the private sector, groups, and individuals, which are part of intercultural dialogue (Signitzer and Coombs, 1992, p. 139). Additionally, Manheim (1994, p.4) details that explaining and defending official policies of a state is the purpose of public diplomacy, as well as displaying a positive image of the state to the foreign public. According to him, strategic public diplomacy is government-public diplomatic activities that revolve around government initiatives to attract public opinion at home and abroad.

Cultural diplomacy is one of the main components of broader public diplomacy, and the purpose of cultural diplomacy is to establish mutual understanding between states through culture. According to Sadowski (2020), cultural diplomacy complements cultural relations, whose basic purpose is to guarantee mutual understanding and collaboration with societies in states to achieve foreign policy goals. He further claims that cultural diplomacy is a significant pillar of foreign policy for European countries. Similarly, Haigh also states that the concept of cultural diplomacy is rooted in cultural relations, and so it can be defined as "steps or initiatives

taken by countries in the domain of global cultural relations.” (Haigh A, 1974 in Grincheva N, 2024).

In this case, Japan, an island country in East Asia, since the late 20th century has been actively engaging in promoting itself through cultural diplomacy to elevate its global standing and promote relations with other states. In 2002, Japan launched its cultural promotion campaign with the aim of promoting its culture abroad and enhancing its image in the international community. In such campaigns, Japan endorses its rich cultural heritage, traditional cuisines, and its unique lifestyle to advertise the image of the state that is attractive in the international society and the foreign public. Through this, Japan attracts foreign tourism to directly formulate an impression through cultural exposure and effective advertising (PDGC2014C, 2015). Additionally, the cool Japan campaign has been a key component for the Japanese government in utilising its Pop-Culture which includes Anime, manga, Video Games, along with traditional culture like Cuisine, to engage with foreign audiences. Due to this, the Cool Japan Campaign is considered a significant factor in Japanese cultural diplomacy. (Snow, 2013, p.6).

The Cool Japan campaign benefits numerous Japanese content industries, which have the potential for enhancing Japan’s cultural identity abroad. The content industries include Anime, Manga, and Video Games, which consist of a global fanbase and act as a medium for cross-cultural communication, along with being promoted as an entertainment source (Snow, 2024, p.54). Additionally, promotion of Japanese cuisine is also included in this campaign. The effectiveness of the Cool Japan campaign lies in the government institutions' active participation and support in promoting Japanese cultural products abroad. Japanese Ministry of Economy, Trade and Industry, Ministry of Land, Infrastructure, Transport and Tourism, and the Ministry of Foreign Affairs, along with the Japan Foundation, which was established in 1972, have actively participated in projecting Japanese positive and peaceful image abroad to gain its broader soft image goals along with economic benefits that follow it (Matsui, 2014).

Pakistan-Japan Cultural Relations:

Pakistan-Japan cultural relations started after the signing of the cultural agreement by both states in 1957. The agreement advocated for providing better facilities to understand the unique culture of both countries and fostering cultural ties. This included cultural exchange programs, cultural events and festivals (both traditional and modern culture) as well as developmental cooperation. The Japan Foundation plays a key role in establishing a bridge between Japanese culture and the foreign audience. As its main purpose is to support Japanese language teaching abroad, cultural exchanges through scholarships and the exchange of artists. In Pakistan, the Japanese department was established to provide a Japanese language course to students in the National University of Modern Languages to fill the language gap between the states and foster cultural understanding (Siddiqui, 2024).

The Pakistan-Japan Cultural Association is a suitable example as it plays a major role in bolstering cultural relations between the two. It organizes several Japanese cultural events and has four branches in major cities of Pakistan. Similarly, the Pakistan-Japan Friendship Forum was established in 2018 to reinforce public relations between the two states and is now held every year to strengthen and showcase the relationship between Pakistan and Japan (Embassy of Japan in Pakistan, 2018).

Presently, Japanese pop culture, including Anime, Manga, and Japanese video games, is becoming popular among the Pakistani public, especially the youth population. Every year, an event is held in which Pakistanis from all over the country participate and cosplay their favourite Japanese anime and manga characters. AniCon and TwinCon are emerging events for Japanese culture enthusiasts in Pakistan (Kazim, 2016). Such events highlight the success and

effectiveness of Japanese cultural diplomacy, which not only benefits Japan economically but also positively enhances its reputation in the international community.

Pakistani Youth's Perception of Japanese Culture

This study is conducted to understand whether the Japanese nation branding through cultural diplomacy is successful in influencing foreign public's opinion to its favor or not. The initial part of the research focused on conceptualizing public diplomacy, cultural diplomacy and nation branding and establishing a link between these concepts which is to influence foreign public to achieve its interest, economy, social and most significantly promoting positive image of the state. This study measures the awareness of Japanese culture among Pakistani youth and their perception of Japanese culture. The measured perception will then identify whether Japanese nation branding through cultural diplomacy is effective, successful or not.

The sample size of the case study was 190 participants, in which 98 were females and 92 were males from Pakistani youth population. The participants that are included in the survey was in between 15 to 30 years of age. The questionnaire consisted of sixteen questions in which there were four demographic criteria, which included age of the participants, their gender, their nationality and lastly, their education. The remaining twelve were statements for the purpose of measuring the Japanese culture awareness, its influence and the perception or understanding of Pakistani youth of Japan via its culture.

To analyze the data Microsoft Excel and Statistical Package for Social Sciences (SPSS) had been used. In SPSS, descriptive statistics were used to analyze the data in which frequencies had been checked of demographics and statement questions. Furthermore, bar charts had been used to represent the data.

Demographic Analysis:

The demographics are analyzed through descriptive analyses and the rest are as follow,

Table and Graph # 1

Age		Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
Valid	15 to 18	11	5.8	5.8	5.8
	19 to 22	99	52.1	52.1	57.9
	23 to 26	63	33.2	33.2	91.1
	27 to 30	17	8.9	8.9	100.0
	Total	190	100.0	100.0	

Data Interpretation:

The frequency table and the bar graph display the age of the participants. The majority of the participants (52.1%) fall within the 19 to 22 years age group, which suggests that this is the most represented age bracket in the sample. The 23 to 26 years age group also has a significant representation, comprising 33.2% of the sample. There is an abrupt drop in frequency as the age increases beyond 26 years, with only 8.9% of participants in the 27 to 30 years age bracket. The least represented group is the 15 to 18 years age range, with only 5.8% of the total participants. The large proportion of respondents in the 19 to 22 years group suggest that the study appeals more to younger adults.

Table and Graph # 2

Gender					
		Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
Valid	Female	98	51.6	51.6	51.6
	Male	92	48.4	48.4	100.0
	Total	190	100.0	100.0	

Data Interpretation:

In the frequency table and the bar graph above the gender distribution in sample is rather balanced, with a slight majority of females (51.6%) participants compared to males (48.4%). This close distribution indicates that the sample does not have a significant gender bias, which is important for generalizing findings across genders in the study. The nearly equal distribution can be beneficial in analyzing gender-related variables since both genders are nearly equally represented.

Table and Graph # 3

Nationality					
		Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
Valid	Pakistani	190	100.0	100.0	100.0

Data Interpretation:

The frequency table and bar graph above show that the sample is entirely composed of Pakistani nationals, with no diversity in nationality. If the research does not require nationality diversity and is focused on a Pakistani context, this data acquired is suitable.

Table and Graph # 4

Education		Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
Valid	high school (9th & 10th grade)	1	.5	.5	.5
	college student (11th & 12th grade)	18	9.5	9.5	10.0
	bachelors	137	72.1	72.1	82.1
	masters	33	17.4	17.4	99.5
	PhD	1	.5	.5	100.0
	Total	190	100.0	100.0	

Data Interpretation:

In the frequency table and bar graph, the majority of the respondents (72.1%) hold Bachelor's degree, which indicates a highly educated sample. A significant proportion (17.4%) has a Master's degree, contributing to the overall highly educated nature of the sample. A smaller group consists of those still in high school (0.5%) or college (9.5%), with only a single respondent having a PhD (0.5%). The distribution shows that the sample is skewed towards individuals with higher education levels, particularly Bachelor's and Master's degrees.

Analysis

Question 1

Are you aware of Japanese culture like anime, manga, Japanese Cuisine (Ramen, sushi etc.) and video games?

		Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
Valid	yes	163	85.8	85.8	85.8
	no	27	14.2	14.2	100.0
	Total	190	100.0	100.0	

Data Interpretation:

In the table and graph above the majority of respondents (85.8%) showed that they are aware of Japanese culture, including anime, manga, Japanese cuisine, and video games. A smaller portion (14.2%) of respondents showed that they are not aware of these aspects of Japanese culture. In the data sample, the high level of awareness (85.8%) shows that Japanese culture has a significant presence or influence among the sample population (Youth population). The strong awareness of Japanese culture among the respondents suggests their cultural exposure through media, food, or other cultural products

Question 2

How often do you engage with Japanese cultural products (Anime, Manga, Games, Cuisine {Ramen, Sushi etc.})?

		Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
Valid	never	29	15.3	15.3	15.3
	rarely	54	28.4	28.4	43.7
	monthly	18	9.5	9.5	53.2
	weekly	31	16.3	16.3	69.5
	daily	58	30.5	30.5	100.0
	Total	190	100.0	100.0	

Data Interpretation:

From the graph and table above, a majority portion of participants engage with Japanese cultural products frequently, with 30.5% engaging daily and 16.3% engaging weekly. This indicates a high level of regular engagement among a considerable part of the sample. 28.4% of respondents engage with these cultural elements rarely, while 15.3% never engage with them at all. Only 9.5% of respondents engage with Japanese cultural products on a monthly basis. The data displays that Japanese cultural elements have a strong presence and influence among the sample, with a majority engaging at least occasionally and a substantial percentage engaging frequently (weekly or daily). This high level of engagement shows that Japanese culture, through its elements, plays a notable role in the respondents' cultural consumption and daily life.

Question 3

Which of the following Japanese cultural products do you most frequently engage with?					
		Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
Valid	Anime	81	42.6	42.6	42.6
	Manga	12	6.3	6.3	48.9
	video games	25	13.2	13.2	62.1
	Japanese cuisine	27	14.2	14.2	76.3
	None	45	23.7	23.7	100.0
	Total	190	100.0	100.0	

Data Interpretation:

In the frequency table and bar graph displayed above, the most frequently engaged Japanese cultural element among participants is anime, with 42.6% of respondents choosing it. Japanese cuisine is the second most frequently engaged category, selected by 14.2% of respondents. Video games are also a popular choice, with 13.2% of participants engaging with them most frequently. Manga is the slightest frequently engaged cultural product, with only 6.3% of respondents choosing it. Primarily, 23.7% of respondents do not frequently engage with any of the listed Japanese cultural products, showing that a significant portion of the sample either does not consume these cultural products or engages with something not listed. The strong preference for anime among respondents suggests that it is a dominant cultural element within the sample, possibly affecting their perceptions and contact with other items of Japanese culture.

Question 4

How has engaging with Japanese culture influenced your perception and understanding of Japan as a country?					
		Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
Valid	negatively	1	.5	.5	.5
	Neutral	75	39.5	39.5	40.0
	positively	71	37.4	37.4	77.4
	very positively	43	22.6	22.6	100.0
	Total	190	100.0	100.0	

Data Interpretation:

In the table and bar above, the majority of respondents have a positive or very positive perception of Japan as a result of engaging with Japanese culture, with 37.4% and 22.6% of respondents, respectively, indicating this. 39.5% of respondents have a neutral perception, meaning that engaging with Japanese culture has neither positively nor negatively influenced their understanding of Japan. Only 0.5% of respondents report that engaging with Japanese culture has negatively influenced their perception of Japan. The data suggests that Japanese cultural products (e.g., anime, manga, cuisine) generally have a positive influence on how people perceive and understand Japan. This is important for studies focused on cultural diplomacy, soft power, or cultural influence.

Question 5

How would you rate your overall interest in Japanese culture?					
		Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
Valid	very low	44	23.2	23.2	23.2
	Low	44	23.2	23.2	46.3
	Moderate	72	37.9	37.9	84.2
	High	16	8.4	8.4	92.6
	very high	14	7.4	7.4	100.0
	Total	190	100.0	100.0	

Data Interpretation:

From the frequency and bar graph above, the majority of participants have a moderate interest in Japanese culture, with 37.9% of respondents selecting this option. 23.2% of respondents rate their interest as very low and another 23.2% as low, showing that nearly half of the respondents have a low or very low interest in Japanese culture. 8.4% of participants indicate a high interest, while 7.4% display a very high interest in Japanese culture. The data highlights that while a major portion of respondents (37.9%) have a moderate interest in Japanese culture, there is a substantial number with low or very low interest (46.4% combined).

Question 6

Has your engagement with Japanese cultural products influenced your desire to visit Japan?					
		Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
Valid	no not at all	7	3.7	3.7	3.7
	no not really	23	12.1	12.1	15.8
	Neutral	18	9.5	9.5	25.3
	yes somewhat	71	37.4	37.4	62.6
	yes significantly	71	37.4	37.4	100.0
	Total	190	100.0	100.0	

Data Interpretation:

From the table and graph, the majority of participants show that their engagement with Japanese cultural products has significantly (37.4%) or somewhat (37.4%) increased their desire to visit Japan, totaling 74.8% of the sample. 9.5% of respondents are neutral, indicating that engagement with Japanese cultural products has neither positively nor negatively influenced their desire to visit Japan. A low portion of respondents display that engagement with Japanese cultural products has had little to no impact on their desire to visit Japan, with 12.1% saying no not really and 3.7% saying no not at all. The data suggests a strong correlation between engagement with Japanese cultural products and an increased desire to visit Japan. This is identifying the effectiveness of cultural items in promoting tourism and boosting a positive image of Japan. Furthermore, a high percentage of respondents expressed a significant or somewhat increased desire to visit Japan.

Question 7

Would you be interested in participating in cultural exchange programs or events related to Japan?

		Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
Valid	Yes	152	80.0	80.0	80.0
	No	38	20.0	20.0	100.0
	Total	190	100.0	100.0	

Data Interpretation:

From the frequency table and bar graph, a major majority of respondents (80.0%) are interested in participating in cultural exchange programs or events related to Japan. A smaller portion of participants (20.0%) are not interested in such programs or events. The high level of interest in cultural exchange programs highlights a strong desire among respondents to contact more deeply with Japanese culture. This could be indicative of the effectiveness of Japan's cultural outreach and the appeal of its cultural products.

Question 8

Has Japanese cultural products influenced your lifestyle, hobbies or personal interests in any way?

		Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
Valid	no not at all	18	9.5	9.5	9.5
	no not really	28	14.7	14.7	24.2
	Neutral	37	19.5	19.5	43.7
	yes somewhat	63	33.2	33.2	76.8
	yes significantly	44	23.2	23.2	100.0
	Total	190	100.0	100.0	

Data Interpretation:

From the graph and table, the majority of participants report that Japanese cultural products have influenced their lifestyle, hobbies, or personal interests somewhat (33.2%) or significantly (23.2%), totaling 56.4% of the sample. 19.5% of respondents are neutral, indicating that Japanese cultural products have neither positively nor negatively influenced their lifestyle, hobbies, or personal interests. 24.2% of respondents report little to no influence, with 14.7% saying "no not really" and 9.5% saying "no not at all." The data suggests that Japanese cultural products have a notable impact on many respondents' lifestyles, hobbies, or personal interests, which could be indicative of the cultural reach and influence of Japanese media, cuisine, and other cultural exports.

Question 9

How likely are you to recommend Japanese cultural products (Anime, Manga, Games, Cuisine {Sushi, Ramen etc.}) to your friends or family?

		Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
Valid	very unlikely	7	3.7	3.7	3.7
	unlikely	13	6.8	6.8	10.5
	neutral	56	29.5	29.5	40.0
	likely	59	31.1	31.1	71.1
	very likely	55	28.9	28.9	100.0
	Total	190	100.0	100.0	

Data Interpretation:

The table and graph above indicate, the majority of respondents are inclined to recommend Japanese cultural products, with 31.1% saying they are likely and 28.9% saying they are very likely to do so. This accounts for 60.0% of the sample. 29.5% of respondents are neutral, indicating they might recommend these products under certain circumstances or have no strong opinion on the matter. A smaller portion of respondents indicates they are unlikely (6.8%) or very unlikely (3.7%) to recommend Japanese cultural products to their friends or family. The data suggests that a significant portion of the sample is positively inclined to promote Japanese cultural products within their social circles, which could indicate strong brand loyalty, satisfaction, or cultural appreciation. The high percentage of respondents who are likely or very likely to recommend these products could be seen as an indicator of the effectiveness and appeal of Japanese culture as a soft power.

Question 10

Do Japanese cultural products make you more interested in learning about Japan and its culture?					
		Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
Valid	strongly disagree	4	2.1	2.1	2.1
	disagree	7	3.7	3.7	5.8
	neutral	56	29.5	29.5	35.3
	agree	76	40.0	40.0	75.3
	strongly agree	47	24.7	24.7	100.0
Total		190	100.0	100.0	

Data Interpretation:

From the frequency table and bar graph above, a major portion of respondents agree (40.0%) or strongly agree (24.7%) that Japanese cultural products make them more interested in learning about Japan and its culture. This totals 64.7% of the sample, indicating a strong positive influence. 29.5% of respondents are neutral, meaning that Japanese cultural products neither increase nor decrease their interest in learning more about Japan. A low percentage of participants disagree (3.7%) or strongly disagree (2.1%), displaying that Japanese cultural products do not increase their interest in learning about Japan for a minority of the sample. The data from sample shows that Japanese cultural products are effective in generating interest in Japan and its culture among the majority of respondents.

Question 11

How effective do you think Japan has been in using cultural diplomacy (Anime, Manga, Games, Cuisines {Ramen, Sushi etc.}) to enhance its national brand?

		Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
Valid	very ineffective	2	1.1	1.1	1.1
	ineffective	2	1.1	1.1	2.1
	neutral	38	20.0	20.0	22.1
	effective	58	30.5	30.5	52.6
	very effective	90	47.4	47.4	100.0
	Total	190	100.0	100.0	

Data Interpretation:

From the table and graph, a significant portion of respondents perceive Japan's cultural diplomacy as very effective (47.4%) or effective (30.5%) in enhancing its national brand, totaling 77.9% of the sample. 20.0% of respondents are neutral, indicating that they neither view Japan's cultural diplomacy as particularly effective nor ineffective. Only a small percentage of respondents consider Japan's efforts as ineffective or very ineffective (1.1% each), suggesting that the perception of failure in Japan's cultural diplomacy is minimal within this sample. The data strongly indicates that Japanese cultural diplomacy, through its cultural items, is viewed positively by the majority of respondents in terms of enhancing its national brand. This shows that Japan's cultural exports are likely contributing positively to its international image.

Question 12

Do you think Pakistani government should learn from Japanese cultural promotion strategies.

		Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
Valid	Yes	171	90.0	90.0	90.0
	No	19	10.0	10.0	100.0
	Total	190	100.0	100.0	

Data Interpretation:

From the frequency table and bar graph, a massive majority of participants (90.0%) believe that the Pakistani government should learn from Japanese cultural promotion strategies. A small percentage (10.0%) of respondents do not suggest the Pakistani government should learn from these strategies. The data shows a strong consensus among respondents that Japan's cultural promotion strategies are effective and could be valuable for the Pakistani government to consider. This could indicate that respondents see potential benefits in adopting or adapting Japanese approaches to enhance Pakistan's cultural visibility or influence.

Conclusion

The Japanese experience in public diplomacy, particularly in cultural diplomacy and nation branding, is one of explicit strategic efforts by the state to build up a positive image and exert soft power in the international arena. Public diplomacy denotes the set of nation-to-nation strategic communication activities through which a state projects its values and culture to other foreign countries in the hope of gaining their goodwill. Cultural diplomacy is a part of public diplomacy, through which the cultural properties of a country are used as means for communication and interaction. On the other hand, nation branding is an all-encompassing strategy for representing one particular image of a country, including its cultural, political, and economic dimensions.

A case in point where such amalgamation has actually taken place: Japan's Cool Japan campaign. Cool Japan was launched by the government of Japan as a public-private partnership to promote Japanese culture on an international level, focusing on the youth. This campaign strategically leverages Japan's cultural assets, that is, anime, manga, video games, and cuisine, to create a unique and attractive brand image of Japan as a modern, creative, and innovative nation. In being sympathetic to the global youth culture, Cool Japan was able to increase Japan's soft power and attracted more attention to Japan's culture and products from the world.

The examination of Cool Japan from the perspective of the nation brand indicates it is a highly successful campaign. Since the marketing of animation, cartoons, games, and food, Japan has been able to present itself as a cultural superpower and its culture exports captured the hearts and minds of youth globally. They take cultural features and go further as symbols of a Japanese identity, signs of the force of cultural influence of Japan.

For example, this cultural diplomacy by Japan on the youth of Pakistan is compelling to trace the global extension of soft power from Japan. Research shows that Japanese culture per se—anime, manga, video games, and food, is appealing to young Pakistanis. This young population is quite interested in the products related to Japanese culture. A positive perception of Japan, as a country is built up. The research illustrates that Japanese cultural diplomacy made deep inroads in Pakistan. It has resulted in long-term interaction with the Japanese culture. This will directly contribute to creating a favorable image and help Japan in achieving its objectives with Public Diplomacy in general. The target audience is the youth in Pakistan. Youths, being the prospective leaders and decision-makers, are also considered a very valuable target segment of a nation brand in Japan over the long term. Since cultural diplomacy in Pakistan is working well for Japan, such strategies could possibly apply to another regional market too, especially the developing markets that have a large pool of youth.

In a nutshell, the use of cultural diplomacy by Japan in the Cool Japan campaign presents before practitioners the power of culture in nation branding. The campaign has not only improved Japan's cultural presence in the global arena but also created a positive and lasting image of Japan among the youth, including in Pakistan. This is why the present study

emphasizes cultural assets for public diplomacy and their potential in shaping global perceptions of a nation. The ability of anime, manga, video games, and cuisine to brand nations shows their effectiveness in reaching and influencing audiences as tools that effectively inspire youth. For other countries especially developing ones seeking to enhance soft power and global standing by cultural diplomacy, the experience of Japan proves essential lessons. The success of Japan's cultural diplomacy, therefore, is indicative of the overall power of culture in its persistent shaping of world perceptions and relationships.

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